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Comparison of two crop sequences with and without legumes in Bulgaria

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Abstract

Agriculture is a major contributor to several environmental problems and pushes the earth system towards its planetary boundary limits. Currently, agriculture's share of total anthropogenic nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P) use has been estimated at 86 and 90%, respectively. Moreover, the use of fertilizers is expected to grow. Low-input systems using legumes in crop sequences are a promising option for reducing environmental impacts caused by N-fertilisers.

We use Life cycle assessment to compare two crop sequences (CS) in Bulgaria; one sequence without legumes (CS1) and another sequence with legumes (CS2). Input data for agricultural production and yields are collected within the Legumes Translated project. We also conducted a plausibility check using a streamlined N-balance for the whole crop sequence (CS) and compared nitrogen recovery and calculated N-emissions based on N-fertiliser specific emission factors. We calculated the calorific value, cereal unit, raw protein and the usable protein (relevant for dairy feed) per hectare for each CS in order to compare them based on the area and product function.

In order to provide those functions CS1 requires 468 [kg N ha⁻¹] mineral N-fertiliser, while CS2 requires just 220 [kg N ha⁻¹] N-fertiliser, which is less than half of CS1. However, from 1.1 to 1.4-times more land is needed for CS2.

Based on area, CS2 causes less environmental impacts as CS1 in almost all considered impact categories. However, a fair comparison is just possible based on the provided function or service. For sake of simplicity, we use the usable protein (UP) to compare both CSs per kg UP. The legumes containing CS2 causes lower environmental impacts than CS1. The main reason is the reduced amount of mineral N-fertiliser needed to deliver 1 kg UP. The production of N-fertiliser is resource and energy intensive, thus causing GHG-emissions and natural gas depletion, but also causes emissions of various N-species, NH₃, NO and N₂O when applied on the field.

Crop sequences with legumes provide an option to reduce environmental impacts substantially due to lower input of agro-chemicals, particularly N-fertiliser but also pesticides. There was no trade-off between the considered environmental impacts. Although the reduction varies among the selected environmental impact categories and depend on the function, e.g. proteins or calories, in both cases legumes in the crop rotation provide environmental benefits, but require more land. Biodiversity related impacts are still work-in-progress but have to be taken into account when competing crop sequences are assessed.

Keywords: N-fertiliser, N-balance, nitrogen recovery, crop rotation, soya, LCA

Introduction

The world population is expected to reach 9 – 11 billion by mid of this century. Feeding the population is a serious challenge given the environmental impacts current agricultural practice has (van Beek, Meerburg et al. 2010). Agriculture is a major contributor to several environmental problems and pushes the earth system towards its planetary boundary limits (Steffen, Richardson et al. 2015). Agriculture drives land use change, freshwater consumption and causes biodiversity loss. Currently, agriculture's share of total anthropogenic N and P use has been estimated at 86 and 90%, respectively. Moreover, the use of fertilizers is expected to grow (Campbell, Beare et al. 2017).

In order to ensure food production and reduce agriculture's environmental impacts simultaneously low-input systems using legumes in crop sequences are a promising option (Schwenke, Herridge et al. 2015). The main advantage is the symbiotic nitrogen fixation and reduced use of fossil energy and N-fertiliser.

Crop rotations describe the chronological sequence of changing crops on the same field. Generally, they strive for maintaining and promoting soil fertility, yield stability and diversification. The physical, chemical and biological characteristics of agricultural soil change with the design of crop rotations (selection and sequence of crops grown, integration of catch crops, legumes, underseeds, perennial plants, green manure, fallow or incorporation of crop residues) (Ball, Bingham et al. 2005). For example, crop rotation influences plant hygiene (by interrupting the risk of spread of plant diseases and pests), nutrient supply (through crop-specific nutrient use, supply of different nutrients through crop residues, etc.) and the humus balance. Incorporated harvest residues and catch crops cause a nutrient transfer and supply of organic matter, improve the structural and aggregate stability and thus the hydraulic properties of the soil and influence the activity of soil organisms.

Crop rotation system produces multiple-products and including crop rotation effects adequately in life cycle assessment (LCA) is still a challenge (Goglio et al. 2018)). There are various approaches to deal with this challenge. The simplest and most commonly used method for evaluating individual agricultural products is to consider a single crop. This approach is used in the EU-RED (EU 2009) and is described in common LCI-data sets (Nemecek et al. 2007, Nemecek et al. 2016, Paassen et al. 2019). This approach represents a product system with two temporally shifted system boundaries for calculating N₂O field emissions (Nemecek T 2007, Stichnothe, Schuchardt et al. 2014).

Another methodological approach for a single crop within a crop rotation is the system division and allocation of input, emissions and crop rotation effects based on specific criteria. The identified crop rotation effects must be quantified and their scope and distribution to the affected crop. Nemecek (Nemecek, Hayer et al. 2015) limit the direct effect to the preceding crop and thus break down the crop rotation into a set of two-tier crop combinations in order to derive new efficient crop rotations.

Another methodological approach for the preparation of a product life cycle assessment of a single crop rotation link consists in extending the system boundary to the entire crop rotation and allocating it on the basis of specific criteria. This involves collecting inventory data for the entire crop rotation and converting the output to a common denominator (Brankatschk and Finkbeiner 2015). They (Brankatschk and Finkbeiner 2014) recommend the cereal unit as denominator and Peter (Peter, Specka et al. 2017)) uses the biogas yield for a cropping system for biogas to allocate environmental impacts to single crops. The latter consider removed straw as to be outside the system boundary owing to the alinement with the EU-RED methodology.

Crop rotation effects can have a substantial impact on the total LCA result of each single crop in the rotation, however, currently there is no harmonized commonly agreed approach, how to include crop rotation effects. In this study, we use a whole-system approach and compare two complete crop rotations, one with and another one without legumes at one agricultural research station in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

We use an attributional approach to estimate the environmental impacts of the two crop sequences from cradle-to-field. All activities and inputs in the period from field preparation to harvest are allocated to the respective crop. Nutrient from crop residues are considered as input to the subsequent crop. For the LCI modelling the latest IPCC emission factors for NH₃, NO and N₂O to air and nitrate to water are used (IPCC 2019) and for phosphate emissions to water the approach of PrahSun (PrahSun 2006). Emission factors for gaseous nitrogen emissions are shown in Table 1.

Tab. 1: Emission factors of N- fertiliser used in CS1 and CS2

% of N-Input	NH ₃	N ₂ O	NO
AN	3.0	0.8	2.9
CAN	1.6	0.7	1.6
NPK	2.3	0.8	2.3
DAP	9.1	0.9	0.7

The Ecoinvent 3.5 database is used for background processes and the RECEIPE_2016 midpoint method is used to calculate environmental impacts.

Input data for agricultural production and yields are collected within the Legumes Translated project (for more details look at www.legumestranslated.eu). CS1 requires 468 [kg N ha⁻¹] mineral N-fertiliser, while in CS2 (with legumes) requires just 220 kg N-fertiliser *ha⁻¹, less than half of CS1. The comparison is done for the whole crop sequences rather than individual crops.

In addition, we conducted a plausibility check concerning the calculated N-emissions based on a streamlined N-balance approach. We assumed a closed-loop crop rotation, i.e. the first crop in the rotation becomes the subsequent crop after the last crop of the rotation and visa versa. The N-balance is calculated based on the following equations:

$N_{input} = N_{output}$, assuming that on average the soil-N does not change for the entire CS

$N_{input} = N_{fertiliser} + N_{atmospheric\ deposition} + \Delta N_{residues}$

$N_{output} = N_{uptake} + \sum N_{emissions} , (NH_3-N + N_2O-N + NO-N + NO_3^- -N + N_2)$

N_{input} from crop residues ($\Delta N_{-residue}$) is calculated as different from residue-N of the previous crop minus residue-N of the harvested crop. The amount of residues and their N-content is calculated based on the yield and factors provided by (IPCC 2006) Vol.4 Ch. 11.

Results and Discussion

We compare two crop sequences (CS):

1. CS1: Winter rapeseed – winter wheat – sunflower grains – maize grains
2. CS2: Soya beans - winter wheat - sunflower grains - winter wheat

We calculated the calorific value, cereal unit, raw protein and the usable protein (relevant for dairy feed) per hectare for each CS as well as their environmental impacts. Results are displayed in Table 2 and the associated environmental impacts in Table 3.

Tab. 2: Functional performance per hectare

Functional performance	CS1 (Without legumes)	CS2 (With legumes)	Ratio CS1:CS2
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LVC [MJ ha ⁻¹]	397628.0	296920.0	1.34
Cereal Unit [kg ha ⁻¹]	21940.9	16023.5	1.37
Raw protein [kg ha ⁻¹]	2844.2	2489.0	1.14
Usable protein [kg ha ⁻¹]	2753.1	2228.5	1.24

For each function (food, feed and/or energy) the area demand of CS2 is higher as CS1, although the ratios differ among the different functions. In order to get the same amount of raw protein 1.14 ha of CS2 is needed and in order to get the same quantity as cereal unit, it is 1.37 ha compared to CS1.

However, in order to provide those functions CS1 requires 468 [kg N ha⁻¹] mineral N-fertiliser, while in CS2 requires just 220 [kg N-fertiliser ha⁻¹], less than half of CS1.

Tab. 3: Environmental impacts of CS1 and CS2 per hectare and per kg UP

Environmental impacts	CS1 [per ha]	CS2	CS1 [per kg UP]	CS2	Ratio CS1:CS2 per kg UP
Metal Depletion [kg Cu eq.]	1.3E+02	4.6E+01	4.7E-02	2.1E-02	2.3
Fossil Depletion [kg oil eq.]	2.2 E+03	1.1E+03	8.0E-01	4.9E-01	1.6
Marine Eutrophication [kg N eq.]	1.1E+00	1.7E+01	4.0E-02	7.6E-04	0.5
Freshwater Eutrophication [kg P eq.]	2.5E+00	1.0E+00	9.1E-04	4.5E-04	2.0
Global Warming Potential (GWP _{100yr}) [kg CO _{2eq.}]	8.9E+03	5.5E+03	3.2E+00	2.5E+00	1.3
Photochemical Ozone Formation [kg NO _x eq.]	6.7E+01	3.3E+01	2.4E-02	1.5E-02	1.6
Stratospheric O ₃ Depletion [kg CFC-11 _{eq.}]	1.3E-01	9.3E-02	4.7E-05	4.2E-05	1.1
Terrestrial acidification [kg SO ₂ eq.]	8.3E+01	4.1E+01	3.0E-02	1.8E-02	1.6

Based on area, CS2 causes less environmental impacts than CS1 in almost all considered impact categories, except marine eutrophication (ME). Nitrate leaching does not occur, when transeaporation is higher than the precipitation according to IPCC, which is the case in Tarnovo, Bulgaria. Therefore, the difference in ME originates from background datasets only. No nitrate leaching is confirmed by a streamlined N-balance approach for CS1 assuming that the soil organic matter and thus the soil fertility remains constant. The overall nitrogen recovery efficiency varies then between 97% and 86% depending on the assumed atmospheric nitrogen deposition (0 to 15 [kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹]). Although the nitrogen recovery efficiency corresponds with the natural variability, the assumption that the N-pool in the soil does not change in the long-term after completing the whole crop sequence is still valid.

The reduction varies among the different impact categories on a per hectare basis, from 29% for stratospheric ozone depletion to 65% for metal depletion. However, a fair comparison is just possible

based on the provided function or service. For sake of simplicity, we use the usable protein (UP) to compare both CSs as UP is more or less the average of all functionalities shown in Table 2. The ratio shown in the right column in Table 3 shows that the legumes containing CS2 causes lower environmental impacts than CS1. The main reason is the reduced amount of mineral N-fertiliser needed to deliver 1 kg UP, i.e. 170 g N * kgUP⁻¹ in CS 1 and 98 g N*kgUP⁻¹ in CS2. The production of N-fertiliser is resource and energy intensive, thus causing GHG-emissions and natural gas depletion, but also causes emissions of various N-species, NH₃, NO and N₂O when applied on the field. That is confirmed by results from Hayer et al., they have shown that introducing legumes to a typical crop rotation consisting of rapeseed, winter wheat and winter barley in France results in lower demand of fossil resources, lower GWP and eutrophication (Hayer 2010).

Conclusions

Crop sequences with legumes provide an option to reduce environmental impacts considerably due to substantial lower input of agro-chemicals, particularly N-fertilisers. There is no trade-off between the considered environmental impacts. Although the reduction varies among the selected environmental impact categories, legumes provide a broad range of environmental benefits. However, the investigated CS2 requires 1.1 to 1.4-times more area to provide the same product service with less environmental impacts.

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